

ULTRAVIOLET ABSORPTION SPECTRA OF SULPHONES. PART II. EFFECT OF CONJUGATION

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The ultraviolet absorption spectra of many $\alpha:\beta$ - and $\beta:\gamma$ -unsaturated sulphones have been recorded and analysed. There is significant conjugative interaction between the sulphonyl group and ethylenic link in the excited state of $\alpha:\beta$ -unsaturated sulphones. In $\beta:\gamma$ -unsaturated sulphones, in spite of the methylene group insulating the two chromophores, the π -electrons of the ethylenic link appear to be considerably perturbed by the inductive effect of the sulphonyl group. The absorption spectra of the sulphones, $X.C_6H_4.CH=CH.SO_2.C_6H_4.CH_3-p$, where $X = p-OCH_3, p-Cl, p-NO_2$ and $m-NO_2$, have been determined with a view to ascertaining the structural effects. The data are interpreted on the basis of the polar effects of the substituents and the sulphonyl group. The changes that occur in the absorption spectra of methylphenyl sulphone on introduction of substituents in the *ortho*, *meta* and *para* positions of the phenyl group have been studied.

In the present investigation the absorption spectra of a number of $\alpha:\beta$ - and $\beta:\gamma$ -unsaturated sulphones in ethanol solution have been recorded. The object in choosing these sulphones is to find out (1) the effect on absorption of extended conjugation involving the sulphonyl group, and (2) the effect on absorption of the introduction of a methylene group between $-SO_2-$ and the other conjugating group. The effect of increased conjugation on K-bands in sulphones may be seen from the absorption spectra recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Sulphones.		λ_{max} .	ϵ_{max} .
(I). Ph.SO ₂ .Me ^r	...	* 217 m μ	6,700
(II). Ph.CH=CH.SO ₂ .Me	...	264	20,700
(III). Ph.CH ₂ =CH.CH=CH.SO ₂ .Me	...	300	40,200
		229	13,400
(IV). Ph.SO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄ .Me- <i>p</i>	...	* 241	17,700
(V). Ph.CH=CH.SO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄ .Me- <i>p</i>	...	280	26,500
		216	18,400
(VI). Ph.CH=CH.CH=CH.SO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄ .Me- <i>p</i>	...	307	33,300
		232	16,800

* K-band only is given.

It may be of interest to compare the absorption spectra of (I), (II) and (III) with those of benzene, styrene and 1-phenylbutadiene (Braude, *Ann. Rep. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 42, 105). The additional conjugation arising from attachment with Me.SO₂- group is seen to cause a bathochromic shift of about 20 m μ in each case. The shift is 40 to 45 m μ when a -CHO or a CH₂.CO- group is attached to phenyl (Braude and Forbes, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 3776; Braude, *loc. cit.*) or styryl group (Gillam and Stern, "Electronic Absorption Spectroscopy", Arnold, London, 1954, p. 126; Lowrey, Moureu and MacConkey, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 3167). The bathochromic shift is about 50 m μ when -NO₂ conjugates with phenyl, and about 30 m μ for -CN and -COOH groups (Braude, *loc. cit.*). Thus, it is seen that the conjugating ability of the -SO₂- group is least among these electron-withdrawing groups. A possible explanation for this

is that in the excited state, the stabilisation for sulphones, arising out of resonance, may not be as high as in the case of nitro compounds, aldehydes, ketones, etc. Structures (VII) and (VIII) make significant contributions to the ground state and excited state respectively.

The formation of a π -bond between sulphur and oxygen in (VIII) involves $3d$ and $2p$ orbitals. According to the principle of overlapping, a $3d-2p$ π -bond is less readily formed than a $2p-2p$ π -bond. Hence, electronic excitation of sulphones does not occur with the same facility as that of aldehydes or ketones or nitro compounds.

The effect caused by the introduction of a $-CH_2-$ group between $-SO_2-$ and ethenyl groups (*i.e.*, the effect of insulation) may be seen from the absorption spectra of the pairs of $\alpha:\beta$ - and $\beta:\gamma$ -unsaturated sulphones (Nos. 1-8) listed in Table II.

TABLE II

Sulphones.	$\lambda_{max.}$	$\epsilon_{max.}$
1. Ph.CH=CH.SO ₂ .Me	264 m μ	20,700
2. Ph.CH=CH.CH ₂ .SO ₂ .Me	294 256 217	1,400 23,400 14,200
3. Ph.CH=CH.SO ₂ .Ph	275 218 215	26,000 16,300 17,100
4. Ph.CH=CH.CH ₂ .SO ₂ .Ph	294 258 212	1,900 23,000 24,500
5. Ph.CH=CH.SO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄ Me- <i>p</i>	280 216	26,500 18,400
6. Ph.CH=CH.CH ₂ .SO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄ Me- <i>p</i>	294 258 226 218 212	1,700 22,700 15,700 19,900 22,200
7. CH ₂ =CH.SO ₂ .Ph	274 267 261 227 225	1,000 1,100 900 13,100 13,200
8. CH ₂ =CH.CH ₂ .SO ₂ .Ph	265 218	1,200 9,900
9. Ph.CH=CH.SO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄ Me- <i>p</i>	280 216	26,500 18,400
10. <i>p</i> -MeOC ₆ H ₄ .CH=CH.SO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄ Me- <i>p</i>	308 230	30,000 20,300
11. <i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄ .CH=CH.SO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄ Me- <i>p</i>	285 220	30,300 17,400
12. <i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ .CH=CH.SO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄ Me- <i>p</i>	298 224 221	23,900 15,900 25,700
13. <i>m</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ .CH=CH.SO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄ Me- <i>p</i>	264 229	37,800 28,700

In compounds 1, 3, 5 and 7, two chromophores are in conjugation. For example, in 3, styryl group is conjugated with phenylsulphonyl group. This conjugation has given rise to a new type of absorption — the absorption is not a summation of the individual chromophores. This is indeed the most important spectral characteristic of conjugation. In 2, 4, 6 and 8, where a methylene group separates the chromophores, the individual chromophores might be expected to retain their spectral characteristics. This is not wholly the case. Thus, cinnamylphenyl sulphone (4) has maximum absorption at 294, 258 and 212 $m\mu$, whilst styrene absorbs at 282, 244 and 211 $m\mu$ and methylphenyl sulphone absorbs at 217 $m\mu$ (Fehnel and Carmack, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 71, 231). There is thus a bathochromic shift of 12, 14 and 10 $m\mu$ in the 282, 244 and 211 $m\mu$ bands, respectively, of styrene. Hyperchromic effects are also observed for all the bands. These spectral changes, occurring in spite of the insulation caused by a $-\text{CH}_2-$ group, must be attributed to the inductive effect of the sulphonyl group.

The spectra of the aryl-styryl or aryl-phenylbutadienyl sulphones can be better interpreted and correlated if the principal absorption band is assumed to originate from electronic oscillations from structures of the type (IX) and (X).

Such a formulation seems to be necessary after examining the spectra of methylstyryl sulphone, phenylstyryl sulphone and styryl-*p*-tolyl sulphone. The bathochromic shift observed in phenylstyryl sulphone, as compared with the spectrum of methylstyryl sulphone, will have to be attributed to increased resonance by the contribution of structure (X), which does not exist for methylstyryl sulphone. A further bathochromic shift, as observed, for styryl-*p*-tolyl sulphone must be expected because the electron-releasing *para*-methyl group increases the stabilisation of the excited state through an increased contribution of a structure like (X).

The effect of substituents in the aromatic nucleus attached to the ethenyl group of phenylstyryl sulphone has been studied from the spectra of compounds Nos. 9-13 listed in Table II. The *p*-methoxy- and *p*-chlorostyryl sulphones (Nos. 10 and 11) exhibit bathochromic displacements, and slight hyperchromic effects. These spectral changes are understandable in view of the fact that CH_3O - and Cl - are electron-releasing in mesomeric structures. The spectrum of *p*-nitrostyryl-*p*-tolyl sulphone (No. 12) needs a more careful analysis. At first sight it may appear that there is a considerable bathochromic displacement with a hypochromic effect (in comparison with the spectrum of styryl-*p*-tolyl sulphone). Since $-\text{NO}_2$ is an electron-attracting group, the bathochromic shift cannot be explained if the electromeric effect operates in the same direction in both Nos. 9 and 12. Actually, the electron-withdrawal by $-\text{NO}_2$ and $-\text{SO}_2$ - groups occurs in opposite directions. The $-\text{NO}_2$ group, being a more powerful electron-attractor, has a dominating influence. The

result is that *p*-nitrostyryl-*p*-tolyl sulphone will have contribution to its excited state mostly from structure (XI) and not from (XII). Thus, the spectrum is more like what is expected of *p*-nitrostyrene.

In contrast with the *p*-nitrostyryl sulphone, *m*-nitrostyryl-*p*-tolyl sulphone has spectral resemblance to styryl-*p*-tolyl sulphone. This is due to the inability of -NO₂ to conjugate with vinyl group in the *m*-nitro compound. The spectral behaviour of Nos. 10 and 11 confirms also the view that the -SO₂- group can conjugate with various electron-releasing groups. Further evidence in this direction is also gathered by recording the spectra of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-methoxyphenylmethyl sulphones as well as *o*-, *m*- and *p*-aminophenylmethyl sulphones (cf. Fehnel and Carmack, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 1292; Backer and Kloosterziel, *Rec. trav. chim.*, 1953, 72, 185, 655). The data for these compounds are summarised in Table III. The low-intensity bands observed around 280 mμ in the case of *o*- and *m*-methoxyphenyl sulphones, and around 310 mμ in the case of *o*- and *m*-aminophenyl sulphones are modified B-bands. The K-bands of the *para* isomers appear at longer wave-lengths and they are of much higher intensity too than those of the *ortho* and *meta* isomers. This is the kind of spectral relationship one would expect for the *ortho*; *meta* and *para* isomers (see Doub and Vandenberg, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 69, 2714; 1949, 71, 2414) if the two substituents in the benzene nucleus have opposite electromeric effects.

TABLE III

Sulphones.	λ _{max} .	ε _{max} .
<i>o</i> -MeO.C ₆ H ₄ .SO ₂ .Me	... 283 mμ 224	4,200 8,000
<i>m</i> -MeO.C ₆ H ₄ .SO ₂ .Me	287 285 283 224	2,900 3,000 3,000 8,000
<i>p</i> -MeO.C ₆ H ₄ .SO ₂ .Me	... 240	16,500
<i>o</i> -NH ₂ .C ₆ H ₄ .SO ₂ .Me*	... 312 245	4,000 8,400
<i>m</i> -NH ₂ .C ₆ H ₄ .SO ₂ .Me	313 309 249	2,500 2,500 7,900
<i>p</i> -NH ₂ .C ₆ H ₄ .SO ₂ .Me	... 268	19,300

* Our data agree with those of Fehnel and Carmack (*loc. cit.*).

EXPERIMENTAL

Phenylstyryl, styryl-*p*-tolyl, *p*-methoxystyryl-*p*-tolyl, *p*-chloro-styryl-*p*-tolyl and *m*-nitrostyryl-*p*-tolyl sulphones were prepared by the method of Balasubramanian

and Baliah (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 1844). Methylstyryl sulphone was prepared by the method of Balasubramanian *et al.* (*ibid.*, 1955, 3296). Phenylvinyl sulphone was prepared by the method of Smith and Davis (*J. Org. Chem.*, 1950, 15, 824). Allylphenyl sulphone was prepared according to Otto (*Annalen*, 1894, 283, 184). Methyl *o*-, *m*- and *p*-methoxyphenyl sulphones were prepared according to Heppenstall and Smiles (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 903). *o*-Aminophenylmethyl sulphone was obtained by the reduction of *o*-nitrophenylmethyl sulphone with FeSO_4 and ammonia; recrystallisation from water furnished colorless plates, m.p. 86-87° (cf. Schimmelschmidt and Thomae, U.S.P. 1,939,416/1933; *Chem. Abs.*, 1934, 28, 1716). *m*-Aminophenylmethyl sulphone was prepared by the method of Heppenstall and Smiles (*loc. cit.*) and *p*-aminophenylmethyl sulphone, according to Goldberg and Besly (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, 569). 1-Methylsulphonyl-4-phenylbuta-1:3-diene, m.p. 89-90.5°, was prepared as described by Shanmuganathan (Ph.D. thesis, Annamalai University, 1956, p. 62).

p-Nitrostyryl-*p*-tolyl Sulphone.—A mixture of *p*-tolylsulphonylacetic acid (4.3 g.), *p*-nitrobenzaldehyde (3 g.) and benzylamine (2.2 g.) in glacial acetic acid (4 c.c.) was gently heated under reflux for 30 minutes. After cooling, the product was treated with 200 c.c. of ether and left overnight. The ether layer was then separated, washed with water and dried over anhydrous MgSO_4 . On saturating the ether solution with dry HCl, a heavy yellow oil was obtained which solidified after a few hours. The solid was filtered off, washed with ether and the filtrate allowed to evaporate. The residue (3.3 g., 55% yield) was dissolved in boiling ethanol, treated with decolorising carbon, filtered, and diluted with water. Crystallisation of the precipitated solid from methanol furnished lemon-yellow needles, m.p. 182-83°. (Found: C, 59.3; H, 4.5. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_4\text{NS}$ requires C, 59.4; H, 4.3%).

Cinnamyl-p-tolyl Sulphone.—A mixture of cinnamyl chloride (18.3 g.) and sodium *p*-toluenesulphinate dihydrate (21.4 g.) in absolute ethanol (40 c.c.) was heated under reflux for 6 hours. Sodium chloride separated after 1 hour. The reaction mixture was poured into crushed ice (200 g.) and the mixture stirred vigorously. A heavy oil gradually separated. It was isolated and treated with 25 c.c. of methanol when fine needles of cinnamyl-*p*-tolyl sulphone separated. The crystals were collected and washed with a small quantity of methanol. The yield was 8.2 g. (30%). Recrystallisation from methanol afforded colorless needles, m.p. 126-26.5°. (Found: C 70.4; H, 5.6; S, 11.3. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_2\text{S}$ requires C, 70.6; H, 5.9; S, 11.8%).

Cinnamylphenyl sulphone was prepared by the same method as above, using sodium benzenesulphinate dihydrate, in 33% yield. After recrystallisation from ethanol, the compound melted at 114-15°. (Found: C, 69.5; H, 5.3. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_2\text{S}$ requires C, 69.8; H, 5.4%).

Cinnamylmethyl Sulphide.—A solution of sodium methyl sulphide (17.5 g.) (Windaus and Schildneck, "Organic Syntheses", Coll. Vol. II, John Wiley and Sons, New York, 1946, p. 345) in absolute methanol (100 c.c.) was heated to a

gentle reflux. The source of heat was removed and cinnamyl chloride (38.1 g.) was added dropwise with stirring at such a rate that a gentle refluxing was maintained. The mixture was heated under reflux and under stirring for 3 hours. The precipitated NaCl was filtered off and washed with methanol. The solution was concentrated on a water-bath under reduced pressure, removing as much of methanol as possible. The residue was distilled under reduced pressure using an efficient fractionating column. About 18 g. of unchanged cinnamyl chloride was collected at 124-26°/14 mm. The fraction boiling at 142-44°/14 mm consisted of cinnamylmethyl sulphide. The yield was 14 g. (64%). (Found: C, 73.0; H, 7.2. $C_{10}H_{12}S$ requires C, 73.2; H, 7.3%).

Cinnamylmethyl Sulphone.—The foregoing sulphide (14 g.) was dissolved in glacial acetic acid (25 c.c.) and 30% hydrogen peroxide (50 c.c.) was added slowly under cooling over a period of 1 hour. The reaction mixture was allowed to stand overnight at room temperature. It was then heated on a water-bath at 85° for 1 hour and poured into crushed ice. The precipitated solid was collected and washed well with water. The product (5.2 g.), after recrystallisation from ethanol, furnished colorless plates, m.p. 125-25.5°. (Found: C, 60.8; H, 6.4; S, 16.0. $C_{10}H_{12}O_2S$ requires C, 61.2; H, 6.2; S, 16.3%).

1-Phenyl-4-p-tolylsulphonylbuta-1:3-diene.—A mixture of *p*-tolylsulphonylacetic acid (10.8 g.), freshly distilled cinnamaldehyde (6.6 g.), acetic anhydride (7.5 g.) and litharge (5.5 g.) was heated under reflux for 5 hours. After allowing the resulting reddish viscous liquid to remain for 2 days at room temperature, methanol (250 c.c.) was added and the mixture vigorously stirred. The pale yellow precipitate was allowed to remain overnight, collected at the pump, washed first with methanol (30 c.c.) and then with water. The product weighed 2.1 g. (15%). Recrystallisation from methanol gave colorless needles, m.p. 138-38.5°. Chedroff and Whitmore (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 1075) who prepared this compound by a different method, report m.p. 134.5-35.5°. (Found: C, 71.8; H, 5.6; S, 10.9. Calc. for $C_{17}H_{16}O_2S$: C, 71.8; H, 5.7; S, 11.3%).

Ultraviolet Absorption Measurements.—The ultraviolet absorption spectra were determined with a Beckman quartz spectrophotometer, model DU. All the measurements were made in 95% ethanol solution. The alcohol was purified by distillation after treatment with lead acetate and sodium hydroxide.